

INTERFACE MOLECULAR ENGINEERING OF CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY : The mechanism of adhesion of carbon fibres to epoxy and related resins results from a complex interaction of chemical functionality, microporosity and active sites at the fibre/matrix interface. The lack of an unambiguous test for the quantification of adhesion and the means of distinguishing between the roles of different adhesion mechanisms have led to much confusion. This paper reports the controlled functionalisation of untreated Type-A carbon fibres by plasma polymerisation for the evaluation of the Cumulative Stress Transfer Function (CSTF) as a measure of adhesion. Coatings prepared by the homopolymerisation of hexane and that of the octadiene are strongly hydrocarbon in nature and inhibit chemical interaction between the fibre and matrix resulting in poorer adhesion than the parent untreated fibres. The introduction of comonomers, acrylic acid, allyl alcohol and allylamine individually to the plasma feed resulted in increased levels of specific fibre surface functionalities and improvements in the degree of adhesion.

KEYWORDS: Fragmentation test, adhesion mechanisms, plasma polymerisation, CSTF methodology, Kelly-Tyson model, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced composites are one of the most important composite materials and are used in a wide range of applications. The behaviour and performance of a composite material cannot be explained only in terms of the specific properties of its constituents [1]. The interphase region between the fibre and matrix is also a component which governs the mechanical and physical performance in composite systems [2].

The single fibre fragmentation test is currently considered a good method to evaluate the fibre/matrix interfacial properties because it provides simplified access to the complex phenomena that occur during composite failure, good reproducibility and simple specimen preparation. The test is particularly well suited for a study of the effects of different surface treatments or sizing on the interfacial shear strength [3-6]. In the test, a single fibre is embedded into a matrix, and a tensile stress is applied uniaxially along the fibre axis which when transferred to the fibre through the interface causes the fibre to fracture. The fibre continues to fracture into shorter lengths as the load increases, until the fragment length becomes too short to break. This situation is defined as the saturation in the fibre fragmentation process. The shortest fragment length which can break on application of stress is defined as the critical fibre length, l_c . Because of the statistical nature of fibre strength, a

single fibre does not break into the fragments of equal size and a wide variation in fragment lengths is observed. The fragment lengths for transparent matrix composites can be measured using a conventional optical microscope.

Models for Estimating Interfacial Shear Strength (IFSS)

The Kelly-Tyson model

The model first described by Kelly and Tyson is generally used to estimate IFSS from the fragmentation test and is based on a force balance [7]. It has been widely assumed that at saturation all of the fragments are debonded or nearby matrix has yielded to provide for a constant shear at the interface. The following analysis can be employed:

$$\tau = \frac{\sigma_{fu} d}{2 l_c} \quad (1)$$

Where d is the fibre diameter and σ_{fu} is the fibre strength at a length equal to the critical fibre length l_c . Early work by Ohsawa et al (1978) provided the background for the semi-empirical analysis of the test-data [8]. The critical fibre length is calculated by

$$l_c = \frac{4}{3} \bar{l} \quad (2)$$

Where \bar{l} is the average fragment length.

The fragmentation test is a very complex single embedded fibre test and several micromechanical phenomena observed in the real life composites other than fibre fracture are also observed during the fragmentation test. Shear yielding of the matrix, interfacial debonding and transverse matrix cracking have been widely reported [9,10]. In fact, the occurrence of these damage events during the fragmentation test makes the conventional data reduction technique based on the Kelly-Tyson model invalid. The limitations of the Kelly-Tyson model as well as other data reduction techniques for the fragmentation test based on the constant shear model have been the subject of several studies [9-13]. At this point, it will suffice to say that the use of the Kelly-Tyson model to calculate interfacial shear strength from the fragmentation test data is highly inaccurate.

The Cumulative Stress Transfer Function

A recently proposed data reduction technique for the fragmentation test, the cumulative stress transfer function (CSTF) technique, assumes that the quality of the interphase is dependent upon the number and length of individual fibre-fragments and that the greater stress is transferred to the embedded reinforcing fibre for the case of a good interphase in comparison to a poor interphase [14]. In this approach, the shear stress at the fibre-matrix interface associated with a fibre-fragment is calculated from the plasticity effect model and converted into a tensile stress using the balance of force argument [15]. A resultant tensile stress profile in the fibre fragment is integrated over the fragment length to estimate the stress transfer function (STF). The value of the tensile stress transferred is summed across all the fibre fragments and normalised to the total length of the fragments. This normalised value is called cumulative stress transfer function or CSTF [14] and can be defined as:

$$CSTF = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{i=N} \int_0^{L_i} \sigma_f(x) dx}{\sum_{i=1}^{i=N} L_i} \quad (3)$$

Tripathi et al [14] have demonstrated that the values of CSTF obtained from the fragmentation test agree well with the fibre surface chemistry. For example, the CSTF value of water-sized, A1100 coupled glass fibre embedded in the epoxy resin is higher than that of water-sized, uncoupled glass fibre embedded in the same resin. In contrast to this, the interfacial shear strength, obtained from the Kelly and Tyson analysis fails to explain the influence of the glass fibre treatment and, furthermore, exceeds the shear yield strength of the matrix [16].

In this study, radio frequency induced plasma copolymerisation of acrylic acid/hexane, allyl alcohol/hexane and allylamine/octadiene gas mixtures is used to obtain a range of functionalised coatings on Type A carbon fibre surfaces. Analysis and quantification of the surface groups was determined by XPS. The single fibre fragmentation test has been employed to establish the relationship between the chemical composition of the fibre surface and the adhesion of the modified fibres to an epoxy resin. The degree of adhesion has been estimated from the Kelly-Tyson model and CSTF methodology for the single fibre fragmentation test.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fibres and Surface Treatments

Type A carbon fibres were supplied in an untreated unsized form (HTA-500) by Tenax Fibres GmbH. This is a high performance carbon fibre manufactured from a polyacrylonitrile (PAN) precursor, with high strength and standard modulus similar to the more familiar Toray T300. The 7 µm fibres are supplied as 500 filament tows, with reported values of the tensile modulus and strength of 238 GPa and 3.4 GPa respectively.

Coatings have been prepared by the direct copolymerisation of acrylic acid/hexane, allyl alcohol/hexane and allylamine 1,7-octadiene onto the untreated fibre [17]. Details of the plasma parameters are given in Table 2. The proportions of the respective monomer gases in the plasma feed were altered by varying the molar percentage of the hydrocarbon monomer, whilst maintaining a constant level of overall flow rate. This was done to deposit coherent polymer layers with variable degrees of functionalisation. The carbon fibres were then mounted individually within the plasma apparatus to ensure coating homogeneity. The details of the plasma apparatus and the polymerisation process are given elsewhere [17]. The fibre surface chemistry has been achieved by using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) [17].

Matrix Resin

The resin matrix has a combination of Epikote 828 (Shell Plc) with Araldite GY298 (Ciba Geigy Plc) in the ratio of 63 to 37 phr respectively. Epikote 828 is a diglycidyl ether of Bisphenol-A and Araldite GY298 is a blend of long chain aliphatic epoxy resin and Bisphenol-A. This was cured with 80 phr nadic methyl anhydride (Stag Polymers and Sealants) and 40 phr Capcure 3-800 (Henkel-Napco), a mercaptan terminated polymer. The

epoxy resin was cured at 80°C for 4 h, post-cured at 130°C for 3 h and left in the oven for natural cooling. The cured resin has an elastic modulus of 3 GPa and a tensile yield strength of 55 MPa. The shear yield strength of the resin, 32 MPa, was calculated from the measured tensile yield strength using the von Mises relationship. The details of the fragmentation test procedure and data reduction technique based on the constant shear model are given elsewhere [16,18,19]. The samples were strained to 10% applied strain. It has already been reported that carbon fibres in this matrix achieve saturation in the fragmentation process early on (typically at 5% applied strain) in the fragmentation test [6]. The mechanical properties of the resin ensure that saturation is reached [20]. At the end of the fragmentation test, the fragment lengths and debond ratios were measured using a microscope fitted with calibrated eye-piece to estimate the level of adhesion between carbon fibre and matrix of each specimen.

Table 1: Summary of coatings and plasma parameters.

Monomer mixture	Total flow rate (cm ³ (STP)min ⁻¹)	Plasma power (W)	Polymerisation time (min)
acrylic acid-hexane	1	10	10
allyl alcohol-hexane	2	1	20
allylamine-octadiene	2	2.5	10

RESULTS

The surface chemistry and morphology of carbon fibres are very complex with a mixed functionality and microporous structure [21]. The thin conformal nature of the plasma polymer deposit provides a technique for occluding the residual chemistry and structure of the as-manufactured fibres [17]. Thereby, any functionality incorporated into the film can be considered to provide the principal adhesion mechanism. The functional group concentrations obtained by XPS from the deconvolution of the C_{1s} peak are given in Table 2. The analysis shows that the thickness of the coating approximates to the XPS analysis depth (5nm) and that analysis refers percentage of surface carbon identified with that functional group. It can be seen from Table 2 that the different monomers can be used to provide specific surface functionalities on the carbon fibre surface of different concentration. Monomer feeds containing acrylic acid leads to a specific concentration of the carboxylic functionality; allyl alcohol, the hydroxyl functionality and allylamine, the amine functionality. The fraction of carbon which is assigned to a specific surface functionality decreases as the quantity of the hydrocarbon monomer is increased in the monomer feed (Fig. 1.). The CSTF and apparent interfacial shear strength values (τ_a) obtained from the fragmentation of these fibres are reported in Table 2 and are plotted as a function of fibre surface functionality in Figs. 2 and 3.

During fragment length determination, the mode of micromechanical fracture was noted and included in Table 2. Four different types of damage events in the fragmentation test specimens were observed at saturation viz. complete debonding (CD), partial debonding (PD), transverse matrix cracking (TMC) and mixed mode (MM) where transverse matrix cracking and interfacial debonding co-existed (Fig. 4.). The stress transfer across the interface in the case of complete debonding was very poor. Hence the contrast given by the polarised light was minimal which is obvious from the figure. However, stick and slip mechanism at the interface was observed which was obvious from the subtle colour difference at the fibre-matrix interface. The fibre breaks are marked on the photograph.

Fig. 1. Variation of the fraction of carbon assigned to specific surface functionalities as estimated from the C_{1s} peak in the XPS spectra as a function of the molar percentage of the hydrocarbon comonomer in the plasma feed.

Fig. 2. Variation of apparent IFSS value as a function of the fraction of surface carbon contained in defined functional groups, deposited using a radio-frequency induced plasma polymerisation with different monomer feeds. CD, PD, MM and TMC represent fracture modes in the fragmentation test specimen (see Fig. 4.).

Fig. 3. Variation of CSTF value as a function of the fraction of surface carbon contained in defined functional groups, deposited using a radio-frequency induced plasma polymerisation with different monomer feeds. CD, PD, MM and TMC represent fracture modes in the fragmentation test specimen (see Fig. 4.).

Table 2 The values of apparent IFSS and CSTF as a function of the fraction of surface carbon contained in defined functional groups deposited in a plasma polymerisation. CD, MM, PD and TMC represent fracture modes in the fragmentation test specimen (see Fig. 4.).

Monomer Composition	Hydro-carbon (mol %)	Surface functionality (%)					Apparent IFSS (MPa)	CSTF (MPa)	Mode of failure
		C-CO ₂ R	C-CNR ₂	C-OR	C=O	C-H			
Untreated	-					92.1	26.9±6.0	1053	PD
Acrylic Acid + Hexane (10W)	0	20.4	-	16.2	10.9	52.5	41.5±7.5	1410	TMC
	0.25	10.0	-	15.7	8.9	65.4	35.9±6.4	1465	TMC
	0.50	6.4	-	14.6	5.8	73.2	28.5±5.1	1183	MM
	0.75	3.6	-	11.0	3.8	81.6	31.1±5.6	1064	MM
	1.00	0	-	4.9	0	95.1	16.3±2.9	629	CD
Allyl-Alcohol + Hexane (1W)	0	2.5	-	22.0	6.6	68.9	30.4±5.4	734	MM
	0.25	1.5	-	23.7	5.9	68.9	24.2±4.3	770	PD
	0.50	-	-	12.0	2.6	85.4	19.8±3.5	579	PD
	0.75	-	-	6.1	-	93.9	18.3±3.3	534	PD
	1.00	-	-	2.9	-	97.1	12.0±2.2	774	CD
Allyl-Amine + Octadiene (2.5W)	0	-	22.8	-	3.6	73.5	38.4±6.9	987	MM
	0.25	-	16.0	-	2.5	82.3	39.8±7.1	1125	MM
	0.50	-	9.2	-	0.9	89.9	28.2±5.0	1015	MM
	1.00	-	-	3.5	-	96.8	11.5±2.0	794	MM

Fig. 4: The different modes of micromechanical failure observed at saturation in the fragmentation test; (a) Transverse matrix cracking (TMC), (b) Mixed mode which including transverse matrix cracking and partial debonding (MM), (c) partial interfacial debonding (PD) and (d) complete interfacial debonding (CD). Fibre breaks are shown by arrows.

DISCUSSION

It can be seen from Table 2 that the untreated unsized carbon fibre has an interfacial shear strength value of 26.9 MPa and CSTF value of 1053 MPa. Deposition of a non-functional plasma polymer coating (hexane or octadiene) onto the untreated, unsized Type A carbon fibres reduces the value of CSTF and apparent IFSS. This confirms that the residual chemistry and microstructure on the surface of the as-received fibres provide a degree of bonding to epoxy resins. However, the residual chemistry and the morphology of the as-received carbon fibre is masked by the thin coating deposited using the plasma polymerisation technique which is evident from the reduction in CSTF and apparent IFSS values on deposition of non-functional coatings. Introduction of functional monomers (acrylic acid, allyl alcohol or allyl alcohol) in the monomer feed causes an increase in values of CSTF and apparent IFSS corresponding to an improvement in interfacial adhesion of the single fibre to the epoxy resin with increasing concentration of specific surface functionalities is shown in Figs. 2 and 3.

It can be seen from Figs. 2 and 3 that an increased concentration of carboxylic and amine functionalities in the plasma polymer coating results in an increased degree of adhesion between fibre and epoxy resin matrix. This is attributable to an increased probability of covalent bond formation from the reaction of surface functionalities with the epoxide group in

the resin. It can be seen that although both data analysis methodologies (CSTF and Kelly-Tyson) show the same general trends, there are some differences. For example, the apparent interfacial shear strength and CSTF values increase with increasing surface functionality up to a point after which the CSTF values reach an apparent optimum degree of adhesion, whereas the values of apparent interfacial shear strength may increase or decrease at high concentrations of functional groups. The CSTF methodology predicts an equivalent optimum level of stress transfer whereas the apparent interfacial shear strength is much less consistent (Figs. 2 & 3). The limiting value of CSTF with fibre functionality can be attributed to an optimum interaction between the carboxylic acid groups on the fibre and the epoxide groups in the resin to provide maximum adhesion to that matrix resin, as shown by the yielding of the matrix (Figs. 2 & 3). This aspect is taken into account in the calculation of CSTF value. However, the apparent interfacial shear strength (τ_a) calculation does not take the plasticity of the matrix into account so that τ_a is invariably larger than the matrix shear yield strength [14].

An improvement in the degree of adhesion relative to the untreated fibre is observed for the acrylic acid and allylamine functionalised coatings. However, the coatings of allyl alcohol are much less effective with a value less than that for the untreated carbon fibres (Table 2). The inference from these results is that the hydroxyl groups do not bond chemically with the resin, and that the small increase in adhesion is a consequence of relatively weak dipole-dipole interactions.

Two specific trends observed in Table 2 (Acrylic acid + hexane, 0.5 and 0.75 mol %; Allyl alcohol + hexane, 0 and 0.25 mol %) highlight the superiority of the CSTF technique over the Kelly-Tyson methodology. It can be seen that the value of apparent interfacial shear strength decreases, rather than increasing, with an increase in the percentage of active surface functionalities. Although this may be attributed to the standard deviation in the interfacial shear strength measurement from the Kelly-Tyson model. However, the CSTF methodology is able to predict the logical trend. This shows that the CSTF technique is clearly more sensitive to fibre surface modification than the data reduction technique based on the Kelly-Tyson model.

It is well known that different modes of failure are observed in single fibre composites at differing degrees of fibre-matrix adhesion [17,22]. It has been previously reported that transverse matrix cracks occur at a high level of adhesion; interfacial crack growth at an intermediate level and frictional debonding at a low level [22]. We observed the same trends in this study (Fig. 4.). However, in some samples, as reported in Table 2, a mixed mode could be observed at intermediate degrees of adhesion where interfacial debonding and transverse matrix cracking co-existed. This appears to occur when the actual interfacial shear strength is close to the shear yield strength of the matrix (Fig. 2).

Transverse matrix cracking dominates the damage micromechanics when the apparent interfacial shear strength (as measured from the Kelly-Tyson model) exceeds the shear yield strength of the matrix (Fig. 2). The CSTF value (the stress transferred to the fibre) decreases with the increased surface functionality when transverse matrix cracking dominates the interfacial micromechanics. Thus the apparent maximum in CSTF value can be understood because at increased surface functionalities, the capability of the matrix to transfer stress to the fibre will be reduced in the presence of a matrix crack, despite the fact that the interfacial bond may be stronger. The influence of these transverse matrix cracks on the stress transferred to fibre end needs further investigation so that a more accurate prediction can be

made. At the moment, the plasticity effect model cannot account for these mechanisms. However, using the CSTF methodology, it is possible to identify “an optimum interface” in terms of its stress transfer capability rather than a “strong interface” inferred from the high value of apparent interfacial shear strength. This so called “strong interface” may lead to brittle fracture of high fibre volume fraction composites, leading to premature fracture without the full utilisation of fibre properties.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, radio frequency induced plasma copolymerisation of acrylic acid/hexane, allyl alcohol/hexane and allylamine/octadiene gas mixtures is used to obtain a range of functionalised coatings on Type A carbon fibre surfaces. The single fibre fragmentation test has been employed to establish the relationship between the chemical composition of the fibre surface and the adhesion of the modified fibres to an epoxy resin. Coatings prepared by the homopolymerisation of hexane and that of the octadiene are strongly hydrocarbon in nature and inhibit chemical interaction between the fibre and matrix resulting in poorer adhesion than the parent untreated fibres. The introduction of comonomers, acrylic acid, allyl alcohol and allylamine individually to the plasma feed resulted in increased levels of specific fibre surface functionalities and improvements in the degree of adhesion. This is ascribed to the formation of covalent chemical bonds between the fibre surface functionalities and epoxide groups with the matrix resin. Within this context, carboxylic acid and amine groups are more effective than hydroxyl groups, reflecting the generally recognised reactivity of these species towards epoxides. The effectiveness of the CSTF analysis (based on the plasticity effect model) for the quantification of interfacial adhesion between Type A carbon fibres and epoxy resin has been demonstrated. A comparison with the conventional data reduction technique, based on the Kelly-Tyson model, for the calculation of apparent interfacial shear strength is also made. The results have shown that CSTF values increase with the increased concentration of surface functionalities up to an optimum degree of interfacial adhesion.

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